

The Longitudinal Impact of Crises on Economic, Social, and Mobility-Related Outcomes: The Role of Gender, Skills, and Migration Status

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The project employs longitudinal data (registers and surveys) to examine the extent to which populations of immigrant origin are affected by crises and explore the mechanisms underlying the effects behind the precariousness of certain communities. Using Swiss and other country-specific data, the researchers will focus on the COVID-19 crisis, as well as on other crises.

The aim is to highlight differential effects in the consequences of crises according to migration status and personal characteristics, the sector of activity, but also taking into account the gender dimension and the role of skills. Additionally, different socio-economic and demographic outcomes will be analyzed.